

THE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE VOLUME OF TOURISM SERVICES ON THE GROSS REGIONAL PRODUCT IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract. Tourism services play an important role in the development of the regional economy and have a significant impact on its gross regional product. Especially in regions with developed tourist networks, income from tourism is becoming one of the main drivers of the regional economy. In this article, the share of Fergana Valley tourism services in the volume of GDP is analyzed.

Key words: tourism, tourism services, gross regional product, volume of services, diversification of services.

Expansion of tourism services, operation of hotels, restaurants, transport and entertainment facilities will create jobs in various sectors and increase GRP. Also, the flow of foreign and domestic tourists contributes to the development of trade, services and other sectors. Therefore, the increase in the volume of tourism services is one of the main factors directly and indirectly affecting the growth of GRP indicators.

In 2010, the total GRP volume of Fergana region was 5417.5 billion soums, of which the share of services was 35.7% of the GRP volume, 1933.3 billion soums. In 2010, trade, living and catering services in Fergana region totaled 340.8 billion soums, transport, storage and communication services amounted to 233.1 billion soums, and other services amounted to 1359.4 billion soums. In 2023, the GRP of Fergana region will be 77,670.6 billion soums, which has increased 14 times compared to 2010. In addition, in 2023, the share of services in the volume of Fergana region's GRP will be 42.3%, it has increased 17 times compared to 2010 and reached 32870.0 billion soums. In 2023, in the total services in Fergana region, trade, living and dining services amount to 12,369.7 billion soums, transportation and storage, communication and information services amount to 4,430.1 billion soums, and the volume of other services provided is 16,070 reached 2 billion soums.

In 2010, the GRP of Andijan region amounted to 4497.3 billion soums, of which 32.0% (1439.6 billion soums) was contributed by the services sector. In 2010, the total services of Andijan region included trade, living and dining services 272.0 billion soums, transportation and storage, information and

communication services 229.4 billion soums, and other services 938.2 billion soums. In 2023, the volume of GRP of Andijan region increased by almost 17 times compared to 2010 and reached 76306.7 billion soums. Also, in 2023, the volume of services in the GRP of Andijan region will be 24,921.3 billion soums (32.2%), of which trade, living and dining services will account for 9,016.3 billion soums, transportation and storage, information and communication services amounted to 3,608.3 billion soums, and the volume of other services amounted to 12,296.4 billion soums.

Figure 1. Dynamics of changes in the volume of total services in Fergana, Andijan and Namangan regions¹

In 2010, the GRP of Namangan region was equal to 3364.4 billion soums, and the share of the service sector in it was equal to 40.0% and amounted to 1346.7 billion soums. In 2010, the total volume of services in Namangan region was 214.1 billion soums for trade, accommodation and food services, 189.1 billion soums for transportation and storage, information and communication services, and 943.5 billion soums for other services. In 2023, the GRP of Namangan region will reach 52,442.7 billion soums, which has increased 17 times compared to 2010. In addition, in 2023, the share of services in the gross regional product of Namangan region was 43.7% and equal to 25083.8 billion soums. In the structure of total services of Namangan region in 2023, the volume of trade, accommodation and food services will be 10713.6 billion soums, the volume of transportation and storage, information and

¹It was developed by the author based on the data of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

communication services will be 285.3 billion soums, and the volume of services of other sectors will be 11544.9 billion soums.

Cultural heritage is of great importance in the field of tourism, and museums and historical exhibits displayed through them occupy a special place among tourist attractions. Visiting museums not only increases the cultural wealth of tourists, but also has a significant impact on expanding the scope of tourism services. Museums, their number and the number of visitors increase the tourist flow and serve to develop the tourism economy. Museums are an integral part of the tourism industry, and they are of great importance as cultural tourism centers both nationally and internationally.

As a result of the rapid development of globalization processes, the interest of tourists in cultural heritage and historical monuments is increasing, and the number of visits to museums is also increasing. This, in turn, greatly contributes to the expansion of tourism services, the development of tourist infrastructure and the revitalization of the regional economy. Museums and the growth of visits to them help to improve the quality of tourism services, create new jobs and develop other tourism-related service industries. Thus, the increase in the number of museums and their visitors has a significant positive effect on the volume of tourism services. Therefore, the impact of museums and their visits on the volume of tourism services is a relevant issue.

According to the statistics agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2010 there were a total of 105 museums in our Republic, the number of visits to them was 4,904.3, and the number of excursions organized by museums reached 76,255. As a result of the number of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan reaching 140 by 2023, the number of visits to museums increased by 16.4% (5711.2) and the number of excursions organized in museums by 27.7% (97394) compared to 2010.

Analyzing the regions of the Fergana Valley, we can see that in 2010 there were a total of 2 museums in the Fergana Valley, 14 museums in the Fergana region, 9 museums in the Andijan region, and 2 museums in the Namangan regions. In 2023, the number of museums in the Fergana Valley will be 26, an increase of 1 compared to 2010.

When analyzed by regions, we can see that in 2023, the number of museums in Fergana region decreased by 3 compared to 2010, in Andijan region by 2, and in Namangan region remained unchanged.

According to the analysis of development trends of tourism services in the Fergana Valley, some positive changes are observed in the field of tourism in this

region. First of all, the rich historical and cultural heritage, beautiful natural landscapes and ethnic diversity remain one of the main factors in attracting tourists. In recent years, the improvement of transport infrastructure, tourism support programs and the focus on international events have significantly increased the tourism potential of the region.

In addition, the development of ecological, ethnic and agrarian tourism in the Fergana Valley is helping to expand the range of tourist services. In particular, local crafts and traditional cultural experiences are attracting interest among tourists. At the same time, modern approaches in the field of service, construction of new hotels and restaurants serve to increase the flow of tourists.

Also, the region has great potential for tourism due to its rich cultural and historical heritage and natural beauty. In recent years, measures to improve tourism infrastructure and government support programs have given new impetus to this sector, which has led to an increase in the number of visits.

Also, the involvement of local population in tourism and the increase of knowledge and skills in the field of service have a positive effect on this process. New types such as ecotourism and agrarian tourism are developing and providing a variety of tourism services.

In conclusion, positive trends in the development of tourism services are being observed in the Fergana Valley. For further growth of this sector in the future, it will be important to improve the quality of service, strengthen international cooperation and develop tourist infrastructure. At the same time, greater results can be achieved by promoting the region's tourism potential globally and attracting investments.

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